

MBD-FREE SITE OPTIONS REPORT

16.08.2023

Link to map:
https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1SLxSXk2QKWJ9vmbQPcO7hIASB5_9P-8&usp=sharing

Kivunge District

Lumumba Regional

Kitogani District

HOSPITAL SITES

LUMUMBA - Front

LUMUMBA - Back View

LUMUMBA - Surrounding Buildings

LUMUMBA - Top View

Reflective glass and white facade to reduce solar gains and prevent overheating.

Aluminium windows with sliding mosquito netting on ground and first floor.

Self closing door mechanisms on majority of doors.

High quality solid doors.

Piped water supplied by small pump station extracting from adjacent shared well, with covered water storage.

Covered rainwater management and treatment. Water used for irrigating the garden.

LUMUMBA - Existing Vector Control Measures

No cross ventilation in wards (single aspect) with no overhang for shading. This is causing these rooms to get very hot and then windows are left open to cool them down.

Glass above ward doors instead of be screened opening to allow air out. Would create issue with air conditioning if unable to seal.

Lifts shafts could create path for mosquitoes.

Large atriums spaces allow mosquitoes to reach all floors.

Note: Air is much cooler in the circulation space. Could add extractor fans to bring that

Wards off atrium do not have external windows, only windows to atrium. They are air-conditioned however.

Some windows in operating theatre do not have screens but are openable - top hung - second floor. There are also multiple wards without air-conditioning and no screening from the second floor upwards.

LUMUMBA - Environmental Mosquito Risks Identified

Lack of fans. Large rooms - approx 5m x 5m with only one ceiling fan.

Stair well is open with no doors and openings. Mosquitoes could reach all floors via the stairwell.

Nurses station open and unscreened with low wall surrounding it.

Gaps underneath exterior doors and no double door entrance lobby to main doors.

Currently no infrastructure for hanging nets

Screened aluminium windows however when half open there is a gap along the length where mosquitoes can enter. Also can only ever have half of the area of the window open or open and screened, reducing ventilation.

LUMUMBA - Environmental Mosquito Risks Identified

Open rain floor drains by ramps.

Concrete floor drains with holes for mosquitoes to enter and difficult to lift and check.

Shower drains accumulate water. Likely to be regularly flushed when in use however.

Gaps around water pipe to water storage by pump station.

Next to secondary school with many areas where mosquitoes are breeding including uncovered sim tanks

School: Open water storage and leaking taps.

School: Washing area with water storage and puddles of water for breeding.

Public toilet for use of security guards with open pit latrines, no ventilated, open and unscreened.

Large area adjacent to site with large depression where many different plants are grown and water collects.

Construction / vacant site next to hospital, could be breeding site for mosquitoes.

LUMUMBA - Environmental Mosquito Risks Identified in the Surroundings

KITOGANI - Front

KITOGANI - Back

KITOGANI - Top

KITOGANI - Surrounding Buildings

Many openings to the circulation area, including perforated facade and large decorating opening on the first floor. Would be very difficult to fully screen.

Most wards and rooms off the circulation space have windows only on 1 facade, preventing cross ventilation. Opening above door is glazed rather than screened also preventing ventilation.

Gaps below doors and no self-closing mechanisms. Glass above doors - not screening preventing any cross ventilation.

2 fans for 6 beds in wards- not above beds and no aircon.

No infrastructure for hanging bednets from ceiling. Some beds have attachments for poles to support bednet.

Floor drains hold standing water in bathrooms. Not an issue if regularly flushed.

Latrines open without self closing pans and water buckets. Not an issue if regularly flushed.

Limited bins (collected 2-3 weeks) and no covered space for waste or incinerator.

Stairwell openings not screened.

No double door entrance and entrance doors kept open.

Large central courtyard that hasn't been levelled out as rain used to collect in puddles. The drain is uncovered and still holds stagnant water.

Screened aluminium windows however when half open there is a gap along the length where mosquitoes can enter. Also can only ever have half of the area of the window open or open and screened, reducing ventilation.

Key points from interviews with maternity nurse, medical officer in charge and two councillors.

- Receiving patients with Malaria (not common) and Filariasis. Not received any patients with Dengue. Malaria patients have travel history in the mainland.
- Haven't received training on protecting themselves in the hospital
- Staff want more insecticide spray and repellent
- No maintenance staff for the garden so all hospital staff help keep it clear and cut the grass. Also mention a lack of equipment to cut grass and upkeep the gardens.
- They have had an entomology team come and survey the hospital. Only found mosquitoes that transmit Filariasis. Did not find Aedes.
- Hospital was fumigated 3 months ago. Kept the hospital running while fumigating. Would like to fumigate regularly
- Challenges with some ward bed designs that do not allow mosquito nets to be hung easily.
- Another challenge is the lack of insecticidal injection for Malaria. We need to have the full coverage of medical to prevent malaria mobility.

Existing Hospital Wards

(Anticipated that this will remain in use)

Mother and Children Hospital

GF: maternity
1F: paediatrics
2F: gynaecology

Clinic run by HIPZ

New District Hospital
(Under construction, same design as Kitogani with minor differences in layout, see Kitogani for MBD Risks)

Pump room and generator

KIVUNGE - Surrounding Buildings

KIVUNGE - Back

KIVUNGE - Top

Existing hospital wards in pavilion style design. It is anticipated that these will continue to be used by staff and patients. Many mosquitoes inside however good cross ventilation. Parts renovated in 2011.

Doors left open in the daytime and closed at night, allowing mosquitoes to enter in the daytime.

Screened windows have multiple tears and openings. No wire mesh behind many screened windows. Some new aluminium windows installed but without sliding mosquito screen. Many louvred windows are broken or missing glass louvres.

Gaps below doors and around some broken windows.

Uncovered drains allowing mosquito entry to stagnant water.

Exterior circulation allowing daytime biting. Many doors left open for ventilation.

Recently built mother and child hospital. Patients and staff complained of many mosquitoes, especially at night. Internal courtyard covered with a glass roof. Concrete block walls with high thermal mass with some overhangs for shading.

Wards have windows only on one side preventing cross ventilation. Glass above doors prevents any cross ventilation. Some wards have air-conditioning.

Screened aluminium windows however when half open there is a gap along the length where mosquitoes can enter. Also can only ever have half of the area of the window open or open and screened, reducing ventilation.

No self closing mechanisms and doors open at during the day and closed at night.

Lack of fans. Wards typically have x2 central fans for 9-10 beds. Patients report that fans help to reduce the mosquitoes however sometimes not all patients agree to have the fans on due to temperature and sound.

No self-closing latrine pan and water stored by latrines. Not an issue if regularly flushed.

Entrance doors remain open and no double door entrance lobby.

Large central atrium and open stairwells allow access for mosquitoes to reach multiple floors. 8 openings at the top to allow for stack ventilation however these are very small.

Air conditioning units leaking condensation water which is pooling potentially create breeding site for mosquitoes.

Gaps around concrete drain covers potential entry point for mosquitoes to lay eggs.

Unscreened ventilation pipes to drains are a potential entry point for mosquitoes laying eggs.

Link to map:
https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1SLxSXk2QKWJ9vmbQPcO7hIASB5_9P-8&usp=sharing

Kituo cha afya Uzini

Kituo cha afya Mwera

Kituo cha afya Fuoni

Kituo cha afya Chukwani

PRIMARY HEALTH CARE UNITS

Uzini - Surrounding Buildings

Uzini - Front

Uzini - Top

Unscreened waiting area that runs through the centre of the building and enclosed either end by steel security grill.

Multiple doors left open and almost all without self closing mechanisms. Some doors that are wood laminate and not solid wood have rotted and created holes through them.

Broken louvred windows leaving them completely open for mosquito entry.

Nursing station (used overnight): hang nets at night but no infrastructure to hang them, no screening.

Anti-natal (before deliver) no protective screening at window which is off the central space, No automatic closure, Fan removed

Delivery room: no screening, only 1 window with no cross ventilation.

Open latrine pan in inside toilet cubicles.

Sim tank cover has gaps and there is a depression around simtanks where water can collect and mosquitoes can breed.

Garbage around building and garden is not maintained with a lot of overgrowth.

Many breeding sites around building where the drains are not covered.

Many breeding sites around building where the drains are not covered.

Covered waiting space

Clinic building

Family planning and youth services

Clinic Toilet Block

Tent covering to create additional waiting space

MWERA - Surrounding Buildings

MWERA - Top

Wards and rooms are single aspect without cross ventilation. 1 fan in centre of room with 3-4 beds in maternity rooms.

Nursing station, where nurses stay overnight night, is open and unscreened in the waiting area.

Wooden windows with Louvres and screening, however screening broken in multiple windows.

Entrance doors kept open for ventilation with no double door lobby space. No self closing door mechanisms.

Outdoor waiting areas unscreened therefore leaving patients vulnerable to daytime biters. At time of survey there were approximately 40-50 patients in the inside waiting area, 25 in the tented area outside, 50 in concrete covered area.

Gaps around drain covers and pipes missing on caps allowing mosquitoes to enter.

Gardens left relatively unmanaged, potentially hiding areas where mosquitoes can rest or breed. Drains not clean therefore potentially becoming blocked and allowing water to collect. They are however open and easy to clear.

Garbage at the back of the site

External latrine toilet without self-closing pan.

FUONI - Surrounding Buildings

FUONI - Street Side

FUONI - Top

Aluminium windows with screening however screening is broken in many areas allowing mosquitoes to enter. Some areas where screening or glazing is missing or has been removed.

Doors are left open to provide more ventilation. Door closers have been deliberately broken to prevent automatic door closure. Gaps below doors.

Exterior waiting spaces and circulation leave patients and staff at risk from day biting mosquitoes.

Some rainwater is collected into a tank with no cover. Simtank is also not covered.

Some rainwater outlets drain onto the ground rather than drainage system or soak away.

Grounds around building have multiple areas with garbage accumulating and plants left unmanaged.

Some windows boarded up to prevent mosquito entry but also prevents ventilation.

Broken louvred windows missing glass panes allowing mosquito entry.

Perforated facade has been screened however adjacent door to exterior is left open during the day (corridor of maternity wing).

TARGET POPULATION FUONI PHCU+ 2022

TOTAL POPULATION	41,488
<1YR (LIVE BIRTH)	1,535
<5YRS	6,057
WRA	10,994
SURVING INFANTS	1,456
UNDER 15 YRS	16,263
GIRLS 14 YRS	565

**PARTNERSHIP STATISTICS DATA FROM JANUARY TO
DECEMBER 2022**

TOTAL ADMISSION	1386
TOTAL DELIVERY	1337
PROLONGED LABOUR	5
APH	0
PPH	13
RETAIN PLACENTA	4
SBF	2
SBM	7
PMTCT (1)	12
TRANSFER CASE	69
ECLAMPSIA	0
HOME DELIVERY	7

FUONI- Target Population and Delivery Data 2022

Incinerator

Toilet Block

CHUKWANI - Surrounding Buildings

*Renovated June 2022

CHUKWANI - Top

Mosquitoes can enter through security grill above the exterior entrance door.

Windows and doors left open with no self closing mechanisms.

Glazing added for security reasons, doctor says thieves can come and jack open the security bars and steal. This glazing prevents ventilation.

1 ceiling fan to 4 beds in maternity rooms. Fan not above beds.

Gaps under doors.

Open latrine pan and drain in staff toilet.

CHUKWANI - Environmental Mosquito Risks Identified

Hidden parts of grounds unkempt with garbage. Rest of site garden maintained.

Exterior toilets block is un-screened with open latrine pans.

Drains around toilet not well covered and allow gaps for mosquitoes to enter.

CHUKWANI PHCU+ KEY STATISTICS MATERNITY 2018-2022

TOTAL BEDS: 6

STAFF LEVEL: 23

NURSE/MIDWIVES: 18

HEALTH ORDALY: 5

YEARS		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
NUMBER OF ADMISSION		358	286	291	230	183
TOTAL NUMBER OF DELIVERY (SVD)		298	254	236	183	144
PERINATAL MORTALITY						
• SBF		2	0	0	0	0
• SBM		4	2	0	0	0
REFER OUT (MIMUJAI)		62	41	44	47	47
COMMON CONDITIONS						
• P. P. H		4	2	5	4	4
• PROLONG LABOUR		6	10	5	5	4
• SEVERE ANAEMIA		3	6	5	5	4
• A. P. H		2	1	1	1	1
• PRE - ECLAMPSIA		10	2	2	2	2
• BIRTH ASPHYXIA		3	0	0	0	0
• PROM		2	6	6	6	6
• RETAINED PLACENTA		1	0	0	0	0
• ABNORMAL PRESENTATION		6	2	2	2	2
• ANC HIGH RISK PREG		10	4	4	4	4
• MATERNAL DEATH		0	0	0	0	0
COMMON INTERVENTION						
• PP. FP		24	36	39	38	38
• IMPLANTIS		22	36	39	38	38
• LUCS		2	0	0	0	0
• IUCS		4	4	4	4	4
PMTCT - 1		294	250	229	178	144
PMTCT - 2						

CHUKWANI - Delivery Data 2018 - 2022

 MBD Risk identified at the site

* - Medical staff are maintaining gardens themselves and lack equipment
 ? - Unknown at time of survey as hospital not in operation

		Hospitals					PHCUs			
		Lumumba	Kitogani	Kivunge - Existing	Kivunge - Mat / Child	Kivunge - District	Fuoni	Mwera	Uzini	Chukwani
Windows	Single aspect, poorly ventilated rooms									
	Large proportion of windows not shaded by overhangs									
	Breakages in screening in windows									
	Broken windows or louvred windows									
	Windows left open	?				?				
	Sliding window screen design that allows mosquito entry									
Doors	Doors left open	?				?				
	No self-closing mechanisms									
	Gaps under doors									
Layout	Exterior waiting spaces and circulation									
	Unscreened interior waiting spaces and circulation									
	Unscreened nursing stations									
Exterior	Gaps or open drainage covers, outlets and vent pipes									
	Poorly maintained exterior spaces with overgrowing plants	?	*			?				
	Insufficient waste management									
Other	Open latrine pans									
	Lack of ceiling fans or not placed above beds									

SUMMARY OF COMMON MBD RISKS IN HOSPITAL AND PHCU SITES